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SPECIFIC FEATURES OF EDUCATION AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE EXISTENCE OF A "TECHNO-DEMOCRATIC INFORMATION SOCIETY"

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Abstract

The research focuses on the fact that changes in industry and technology necessitate the restructuring of educational institutions at all times to meet both the needs of society and the workforce needed by various sectors with the necessary skills, and that education, in line with industrial revolutions, is undergoing a development process from Education 1.0 to Education 4.0. It is also emphasized that Education 4.0 means the realization of a digital revolution in education, and Education 4.0 serves to prepare specialists who will operate in a global and digital work environment during the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

The article argues that Education 4.0 is an education system that can meet the requirements of Industry 4.0, benefit from digital technology, use personal data and open source content, have features that can meet the needs of a globally interconnected technological world, provide continuous learning for students throughout their school years and from there to their working lives, and allow them to take an important place in the world and make a difference.

The research paper provides a scientific commentary on education (Education 4.0 system) and the specific features of its implementation in the context of the existence of a "techno-democratic information society".

Keywords: industrial revolution, Industry 4.0, information society, digital technology, digital and technological literacy, information culture, education of the future, Education 4.0 system, cyber-physical systems, smart teaching tools.

Relevance of the research topic. There is a dialectical "cause-effect" relationship between the existence and development of a "techno-democratic information society" and the training of individuals who think independently and creatively about reality, have deep knowledge, are modern-minded, and are competitive. The existence of a dual-faceted information society is conducive to the training of individuals who think independently and creatively about reality, have deep knowledge, are modern-minded, and are competitive. Thanks to the theoretical and practical activities of competent and professional personnel who deeply master scientific knowledge through their own efforts and thinking, and who are able to creatively apply theory in practice, the information society is moving towards more perfect development. The above-mentioned gives grounds to say that the transformation of the "cause-effect" dialectical dependence between the existence and development of the "Techno-democratic information society" and the upbringing of individuals who think independently and creatively about life, have deep knowledge, are modern-minded and competitive, into a reality in the process of implementing education is a perennial and urgent problem of a general pedagogical nature.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting the research, L. Bertalanfi's "Idea of System Analysis" [1; 8] was used as a methodological basis, and the "System-structural approach", which has

been formed as an important branch of dialectics and has risen to the level of its alternative, empirical-theoretical and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations were used.

Introduction. Since the beginning of time, man, despite being a part of it, has been in conflict with reality - nature. In order to make himself and society strong, he has embarked on a struggle to create techniques and technologies that he has developed from primitive to perfect. He has turned science into an independent field of activity and brought the spirit of revolutionary changes to industry. The development of technology has led to the fourth industrial revolution. Currently, there is a system called the "techno-democratic information society" that makes people more powerful.

This revolution, called the Fourth Industrial Revolution or "Industry 4.0", is characterized by the growth and development of digital systems, artificial intelligence, and virtual connections. The specific feature of the society in question is that all its members have an information culture, are provided with sufficient information in an appropriate manner, and provide high-level information services.

By the way, let us emphasize that information culture is the knowledge and habits necessary for a person to adapt to the information society. Currently, this concept primarily refers to the ability to use

information technologies and the need for them. In the information society, a person is considered "cultured" if he can use information technologies. The role of the computer network in the formation of information culture is great. Information culture: is the ability to use information resources and information communication tools of society; is the application of advanced achievements in the field of informatization and the development of information technology tools in society; is the ability to obtain and transmit information using modern technical means and methods, computer technologies. [2; 14]

The gradual disappearance of boundaries between people and electronic resources leads to their impact on various sectors. There is no doubt that information technologies play a significant role in building a legal state, creating a strong economy, increasing the defense power of the country in which they are located, improving the well-being of the population, ensuring its development, and solving other issues. The information society, unlike the industrial society, is a more intellectual society and creates conditions for the highly educated, skilled, determined, and comprehensive development of people. The application of digital technology in all areas of socio-economic life allows economists, politicians, sociologists, scientists, etc. to talk about the IV industrial revolution. Studies show that, unlike previous industrial revolutions, the Fourth Industrial Revolution, based on network technologies, will have more large-scale and complex consequences. [3]

It is necessary to be ready for change and prepare human resources that can compete globally. Improving the quality of human resources through education is one way to prevent the problems brought by the Fourth Industrial Revolution. [4]. This solution is characterized by the quality of the processes implemented in the education system. Everyone working in this field is required to have experience, the ability to adapt to new technologies and global problems. It is logical that traditional training should be replaced by teaching based on modern technology and human resources...

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials. The Fourth Industrial Revolution is having an impact on the education system as well as on the socio-economic fields. In line with the industrial revolutions, "education, which is a process of sharing understanding and experience of change" has developed in stages (including the specific characteristics of industrial revolutions). The era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution requires an education system that can shape a generation that is creative, innovative, and globally competitive. Currently, the impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on the educational process and the issue of "education of the future" are being discussed on various platforms, and appropriate necessary steps are being taken. [5;92-97]

It is worth emphasizing that the expected paradigm shifts in the education system and the implementation of global education reform have been further accelerated by the impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The main goal of the Fourth Industrial Revolution is to provide comfort in all areas

and facilitate the lifestyle. It is possible to see "smart factories" where production processes and devices are operated with the support of software without the physical power of humans and only robots operate. [6;238-254]

The basis of the smart manufacturing model is the decentralization and localization of production, and the design of products specifically for the individual.

It is necessary to distinguish two main reasons for the reforms carried out in the education system in response to the challenges of the fourth industrial revolution. The first is to cultivate a workforce that has the knowledge (information) and skills to meet the needs of a rapidly changing global economy, and the second is to establish an education system that can produce the productive forces (labor force) necessary for the development of the information society during the industrial revolution. [7]

The education system is faced with the demand to prepare learners for rapid economic and social changes, jobs that do not yet exist, undiscovered technologies, and the ability to understand unexpected social problems in a timely manner and to overcome them competently. [4]

Therefore, the education system must be continuously adjusted to meet this demand and focus on these goals. In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, education must have the potential, complex and dialectical capabilities to develop society.

As we have highlighted above, the Fourth Industrial Revolution has different implications for different areas of our lives. From this perspective, there are both opportunities and challenges for education. The use of different technologies such as IoT, 3D printing, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, etc. allows for more effective transmission of information and the development of a new educational framework. [8;78-94]

This new system aims to create a sustainable environment that will empower a creative, innovative and experienced workforce with the capabilities of Industry 4.0 and accelerate its adoption in manufacturing. The technologies emerging from the 4th industrial revolution are changing the way individuals live, work, etc., and are challenging them to acquire the skills to work with these technologies. Educational institutions should ensure that learners acquire digital and technological literacy in addition to acquiring knowledge. It should be noted that the term "digital literacy" was first used by Gilster to mean the ability to understand and use information from digital sources in various contexts. [7]

It is known that technological literacy includes the ability to use information and communication technologies. Digital education allows people to participate independently in social life. In addition, digital education helps companies compete globally. The reality of the digital revolution requires fundamental changes in the forms and methods of moral education, leading to the transformation of digital skills into the most important abilities. [10;58-64]

Developing digital skills is essential to ensure that they can safely and effectively engage with digital

technologies in the future. Education systems need to take a comprehensive and holistic approach, supporting all learners to develop the skills to be active and ethical users of digital technologies. [11;57-79]

In order to ensure accessibility to digital technologies, BYOD (Bring Your Own Device) strategies are used to provide students with devices that they can use at school and at home. A number of steps can be taken to develop digital skills, such as updating the curriculum, developing learning frameworks, involving educators in training, and developing digital educational resources. [9]

Digitally empowered learners can learn with peers from around the world and develop solutions to problems as a team. There is no doubt that developing learners' digital skills will enable them to participate more actively in society as digital citizens in the future. [9], [11; 57-79]

In order for students to be able to demonstrate their skills and abilities in new fields emerging under the influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it is necessary to implement fundamental changes in technology and taught subject programs. By reviewing the teaching points (plans) of subjects formed on the basis of chemistry, biology, physics, etc., which are considered "basic sciences" in the new curricula, more attention should be paid to the teaching of computer science subjects, which play a key role in the formation of the literacy of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Naturally, more space should be given to the teaching of the subjects in question. [14;432-466]

Due to the rapid development of technology, the knowledge and skills that students learn during their education become obsolete by the time they graduate. In scientific and technical education, it is necessary to educate students and prepare them for the digital environment to help develop and shape the use of today's fastest-growing technologies. Adapting to a rapidly changing environment will require the learner to engage with educational institutions even after graduation, providing both workers with updated skills and young learners (and faculty) with a new direction in relation to the rapidly changing realities of the industrial and corporate sectors. [12; 25-30], [13;579-592]

By the way, let us emphasize that the formation of metacognitive skills in students is of particular importance in the continuous updating of knowledge and skills in line with the challenges of the times. Self-monitoring, self-regulation, and self-evaluation are metacognitive skills, and are related but distinct concepts. Self-monitoring involves observing and tracking a person's actions, behaviors, and cognitive processes during a task. Here, the learner does not try to control himself, does not judge or evaluate his own performance. He simply observes himself and collects information about his performance. Self-assessment is the process of monitoring and managing one's cognition, emotional state, and behavior to achieve goals. Self-assessment is the process of making judgments or evaluating one's own performance or learning. In summary, self-monitoring is about observation and awareness, self-regulation is about actively managing cognitive and emotional processes

to achieve goals, and self-evaluation is about making judgments and reflecting on one's performance. Overall, these are metacognitive skills that allow individuals to become more effective learners by understanding and controlling their own learning processes. [15; 50] A person who possesses metacognitive skills is able to overcome the difficulty of adapting to a rapidly changing environment, and by taking advantage of empirical, empirical-theoretical, and theoretical methods of scientific cognition (by putting their cognitive capabilities into action), they are able to present a new direction related to rapidly changing realities in the industrial and corporate sectors. In connection with Industry 4.0, we would not be wrong to say that "innovation is beginning to dominate education systems." Educational institutions will have to see innovation not only as a means of ensuring increased global competitiveness as a result of the impact of globalization, but also as one of the key parts of the education system. In line with the demands of the times, the teaching of new technologies will be logically accepted as one of the basic needs. "Lifelong learning" will be the main motto of the education system.

The 21st century is the century of globalization. It is natural that the content of education should also take into account 21st century skills: in addition to knowledge, the development of abilities and skills such as complex problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, leadership, digital literacy, emotional intelligence, global citizenship, collaboration, discussion, judgment and decision-making will also be considered as key learning outcomes. [4]

Along with the economic development brought about by the industrial revolutions, information and communication technologies are also undergoing a significant development process. This rapid development and change, while bringing with it global competition and cooperation, plays a major role in both the daily lives of individuals and the process of creating a digital society. Compared to the previous society, this newly emerging digital society has completely changed the concept of time and space and is transforming individuals into individuals who can adapt to a constantly renewing life.

Changes in industry and technology have necessitated the restructuring of educational institutions in each era to equip both the needs of society and the workforce needed by various sectors with the necessary skills. In line with the industrial revolutions, education has also undergone a development process from Education 1.0 to Education 4.0. Education 4.0, as in other fields, means the realization of a digital revolution in education. Education 4.0 serves to prepare specialists who will operate in a global and digital work environment during the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Education 4.0 is the name given to the new education system that can meet the requirements of Industry 4.0: It is a new system that benefits from digital technology, uses personal data and open source content, and has features that can meet the needs of a globally interconnected technological world; It is an education system that ensures continuous learning for

students throughout their school years and into their working lives, enabling them to take an important place in the world and make a difference. [10; 58-64], [12;25-30]

Education 4.0 promotes education in a different way, mainly using technology-based tools and resources. Education 4.0 should serve to develop the skills to use new technologies that help learners develop in accordance with changes in society. [5; 92-97]. Learners should not only be able to read and write, but also be equipped with knowledge and skills that they can use throughout their lives. Thus, the current (modern) education system must respond to changes in the social and economic environment to meet the needs of human capital. It is logical that Education 4.0 aims to prepare individuals to be creative and innovative.

Education should adapt to the environment in which learners live, providing them with a secure and successful future. Education 4.0 uses unique technologies and tools to meet these challenges and helps learners develop themselves in line with changes in society. Therefore, Education 4.0 is a more realistic and practical learning approach that can produce high results for learners' learning. Adapting to a rapidly changing world is essential, and Education 4.0 is the system that educational institutions are using to ensure this. This new system uses "smart" school management systems, learning management software, communication tools, and teaching (teaching) tools. [10; 58-64]

The most important goal of Education 4.0 for all educational institutions is to motivate learners and improve their learning outcomes. Learners can use technology to better communicate with other stakeholders in the system, such as educators, management, etc. The learning outcomes of learners are directly proportional to the level of implementation of Education 4.0. [16; 147-171] The methods and tools that support this system ensure that learners learn more effectively.

Education 4.0 is a future-oriented approach that ensures that learners are shaped to meet the uncertain, complex and technological needs of the future in accordance with the phenomena that have entered our lives, such as cyber-physical systems, robotics, Big Data, artificial intelligence, nanotechnology, global citizenship, etc., and the concept of Industry 4.0. [16; 147-171], [17; 92-98]

In the Education 4.0 approach, it has been determined that, by moving away from constructivist education systems and Benjamin Bloom's taxonomy (which has been present in pedagogical thought since the 1960s), a teaching process based on the following areas will be applied: 1) 3R (Recalling, Relating, Refining), which regulates understanding; 2) 3I (Inquiring, Interacting, Interpreting), which encourages research; 3) 3P (Participating, Processing, Presenting), which is based on drawing conclusions.

Education 4.0 is a "smart" and digital revolution in the implementation of the educational process, which is a key component for the benefit of functional parties (stakeholders). Education 4.0 introduces the best methods and forms in terms of the educational process, modernizes these components, reduces the

administrative burden by automating many processes. In addition, it aims to increase the skills of educators and improve the learning outcomes of learners. [10; 58-64]

In summary, let us emphasize that Education 4.0 is a future-oriented approach and has the following characteristics: 1) learning regardless of time and place (lifelong learning, e-learning, etc.); 2) the opportunity to receive personalized education according to the skills and abilities of students; 3) taking into account the suggestions of students when preparing the curriculum; 4) the predominance of project-based learning; 5) forming students' ability to conduct analysis on large-scale data (Big Data); 6) assessing students' knowledge in the process of applying it to projects; 7) the transformation of new developing technologies into a part of the education system, etc.

There is no denying that in the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, "smart" educational tools and resources should enable individuals to acquire more advanced experience, knowledge, and skills, and to reveal their innovative perspectives. [18;40-45]

Scientific novelty of the study: 1. It has been emphasized that the "techno-democratic-information society" is the basis, and the process of educating individuals who think independently and creatively, have deep knowledge, are modern-minded and competitive, is the superstructure of this basis; 2. Referring to this approach, the idea of the existence of a "cause-effect" dialectical dependence between the information society and the process of implementing education (as a form of scientific cognition) was put forward; 3. The necessity for the process of implementing education in a society that is adequately formed to the challenges of industrial revolutions to be in accordance with the dialectical dependence in question presupposes the existence of an ever-present topical problem of a general pedagogical nature; 4. The existence of a perennial, topical problem of a general pedagogical nature creates the basis for protecting the "Science of Pedagogy", which develops by cumulative law, from the danger of "becoming saturated".

Practical significance of the research. In the conditions of the existence of a "techno-democratic information society", the identification of the specific features of education and the way it is implemented provides a methodological assistance to the practical teacher in the preparation and implementation of a methodological system for the effective organization and management of the educational process.

The result. 1. Education 4.0 is a new system that benefits from digital technology that can meet the requirements of Industry 4.0, uses personal data and open source content, and has features that can meet the needs of a globally interconnected technological world; 2. Education 4.0 is a future-oriented approach and has unique characteristics; 3. The "smart" educational tools and resources applied in the Education 4.0 system, which was formed during the Fourth Industrial Revolution, should allow individuals to acquire more advanced experience, knowledge and skills and reveal their innovative perspectives.

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